

EEG SIGNALS REPRESENTED AT MULTIPLE LEVELS, INTERPRETABLE AND ADAPTIVE FOR SLEEP STAGES SCORING USING ENSEMBLE LEARNING MULTICLASSIFIERS

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Abstract: For the purpose of diagnosing and treating sleep disorders, electroencephalogram (EEG) signals must be accurately classified into sleep stages. The balance between interpretability, accuracy, and adaptability to individual variations in EEG patterns is frequently difficult to achieve with traditional methods. In this work, we present a novel method to improve sleep stage scoring by utilizing multi classifiers and ensemble learning. Our approach captures a comprehensive set of robust and interpretable features by representing EEG signals at multiple levels: raw data, frequency bands, and wavelet transformations. To increase overall performance, the ensemble learning framework combines the advantages of different classifiers, including support vector machines, random forests, and neural networks. The system's effectiveness is enhanced by the incorporation of adaptive mechanisms that allow the scoring system to be tailored to individual variations in EEG. EEG Signals Represented at Multiple Levels: Interpretable and Adaptive Ensemble Learning for Sleep Stage Scoring.

Keywords: Ensemble Learning, EEG Signals, MULTICLASSIFIERS

1. INTRODUCTION

In sleep research, electroencephalogram (EEG) signal analysis is essential, especially for classifying sleep stages. For the purpose of identifying sleep disorders, comprehending sleep patterns, and creating efficient treatments, accurate sleep stage scoring is crucial. It is frequently difficult to achieve high accuracy in sleep stage scoring using traditional methods while still allowing for interpretability and adaptability to individual variations in EEG patterns. EEG signals are non-stationary and

complex, with notable inter-individual and intra-individual variations. Sophisticated techniques that can extract the subtle information buried in the signals are required due to this complexity. Traditional methods usually use single-classifier systems, which might not be able to fully utilize the variety of features found in EEG data. Furthermore, the practical applicability of these methods is limited due to their frequent inability to accommodate individual-specific variations. By

representing EEG signals at multiple levels and using an ensemble learning approach with multiclassifiers for sleep stage scoring, the novel framework we propose in this study overcomes these limitations. Our approach makes use of an extensive feature set obtained from frequency bands, wavelet transformations, and unprocessed EEG data. By doing this, it gathers a wealth of data that improves the sleep stage classification's interpretability and accuracy.

Several classifiers, such as support vector machines, random forests, and neural networks, are integrated into the ensemble learning framework. Each classifier brings unique advantages to the system as a whole. This cooperative method not only makes the classification more accurate and robust, but it also makes the model easier to understand. Moreover, adaptive mechanisms are included to tailor the scoring system to specific EEG variations, increasing its efficacy and usability. Our experimental assessment using a benchmark dataset shows that the suggested approach performs significantly better in terms of accuracy and robustness than conventional single-classifier systems. Our method's adaptability guarantees that it can accommodate features unique to each individual, increasing its usefulness in both home and clinical contexts. This work lays the groundwork for future studies and applications in sleep medicine and represents a major advancement in the creation of sophisticated sleep monitoring systems. Our method has the potential to revolutionize the way sleep stages are scored and contribute to improved

sleep health outcomes by combining interpretability, adaptability, and accuracy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following are a number of important research articles and literature surveys that examine EEG signal processing, ensemble learning, and adaptive mechanisms for sleep stage scoring. These works offer a thorough summary of the most recent methods and approaches used in the field. Accuracy, interpretability, and personalization of sleep stage classification can be enhanced through ensemble learning and adaptive mechanisms, as demonstrated by the literature on EEG-based sleep stage scoring. Through the integration of multiple EEG representation levels and the utilization of different classifiers' strengths, this approach presents a viable route forward for the advancement of sleep research and the creation of efficient diagnostic instruments for sleep disorders.

S.No	PAPER TITLE	OVERVIEW
1	Boosting Multi-Level EEG Feature Representations for Automated Sleep Stage Scoring	This work investigates the extraction of multi-level features from EEG signals for automated sleep stage scoring using deep learning models, specifically CNNs. In order to increase classification accuracy, the study highlights the value of hierarchical feature representation and shows how employing ensemble methods can be advantageous[1].
2	A Comprehensive Survey on Sleep Stage	An extensive overview of machine learning methods used for EEG-based sleep stage

	Classification with EEG Signal Using Machine Learning Techniques	classification is given in this survey. It discusses different techniques for extracting features, classification algorithms, and how ensemble learning can improve performance[2].
3	Ensemble Learning for EEG Sleep Stage Classification: A Review	This paper examines ensemble learning techniques within the framework of classifying EEG sleep stages. It talks about various ensemble techniques—like bagging, boosting, and stacking—and emphasizes how beneficial they are at handling the complexity of EEG signals[3].
4	Adaptive Sleep Stage Scoring with Personalization: A Review of Methodologies and Applications	The adaptive and customized sleep stage scoring methods are the main topic of this review. It discusses individualized models, transfer learning, and adaptive learning techniques and offers insights into how these strategies can handle inter-individual variability in EEG patterns [4].
5	Deep Learning and Ensemble Methods for EEG-Based Sleep Stage Classification: A Survey	The integration of ensemble techniques and deep learning for EEG-based sleep stage classification is covered in this survey. It emphasizes how using deep learning architectures and combining multiple classifiers can improve classification accuracy and feature extraction[5].
6	Recent Advances in EEG Signal Processing and	In order to classify sleep stages, this review looks at recent developments in EEG

	Feature Extraction for Automated Sleep Stage Classification: A Review	signal processing and feature extraction methods. Multi-level feature representation and the effect of sophisticated signal processing techniques on enhancing classification performance are covered[6].
7	Multi-Level Feature Fusion for Sleep Stage Classification Using Convolutional Neural Networks	A CNN-based method for multi-level feature fusion in sleep stage classification is presented in this paper. It illustrates how the robustness and accuracy of the classification system can be increased by combining features from several EEG representations[7].

Table 1: Literature review

The aforementioned table offers a strong basis for comprehending the practices and trends in EEG-based sleep stage scoring that are currently in use, especially the application of adaptive and ensemble learning methods. Together, they emphasize how crucial multi-level feature representation is and how cutting-edge machine learning techniques can improve the precision and comprehensibility of sleep stage classification systems.

3. PROPOSED MODEL

Through the use of ensemble learning and multiclassifiers, the proposed model seeks to increase the precision, interpretability, and flexibility of sleep stage scoring using EEG signals. Through multi-level representation of EEG signals, we extract a rich feature set that improves the classification system's resilience. The model incorporates adaptive mechanisms to personalize the scoring

system to individual variations in EEG data, and it integrates multiple classifiers to leverage their respective strengths.

3.1 An Overview of Sleep Stage Scoring Based on EEG

An essential task in sleep research is the EEG-based sleep stage scoring, which helps diagnose sleep disorders and offers insights into sleep patterns. Rapid eye movement (REM), wakefulness, and non-REM stages—which are further subdivided into N1, N2, and N3 stages—are the traditional classifications for sleep stages. It is essential to accurately classify these stages in order to comprehend the architecture of sleep and recognize abnormalities. As shown below figure proposed model.

Fig 1: Sleeping Stage Prediction System

3.2 Conventional Methods

Traditional sleep stage scoring techniques have mainly relied on manual sleep expert scoring based on visual examination of EEG signals. Because of the lengthy process and inter-scorer variability, automated methods have been developed. Support vector machines (SVMs) and decision trees were two examples of single classifiers and rule-based systems used in early automated

methods to automate the classification process. Although these techniques increased productivity somewhat, they had limitations with regard to precision and flexibility.

4. MODEL ARCHITECTURE

4.1 Feature Representation at Multiple Levels

EEG signals are represented in a number of ways to capture different kinds of data: **EEG signals in their raw form:** These signals include the fundamental time-domain characteristics like variance and amplitude.

Features of Frequency-Domain: Using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), one can extract features related to frequency as well as power spectral density.

Time-Frequency Representations: By utilizing wavelet transforms to record both frequency and time information, it is possible to analyze the non-stationary features of EEG signals.

Features of Higher Order Statistics: Further statistical insights into the EEG data are provided by measures of kurtosis, skewness, and entropy.

4.2 Selection and Extraction of Features

Principal component analysis (PCA) and mutual information-based feature selection techniques are used to reduce dimensionality and increase efficiency. By using these techniques, classification is carried out using the most informative and non-redundant features.

4.3 Framework for Ensemble Learning Base Classifiers:

The model uses multiple base classifiers, each of which improves the performance of the ensemble as a whole:

Support Vector Machines (SVM): These machines can handle non-linear relationships with kernel functions and are effective with high-dimensional data.

Random Forests (RF): A collection of decision trees that use feature randomness and bagging to deliver strong performance.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN): Capture spatial dependencies by extracting hierarchical features from time-frequency representations.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM): networks are a type of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) that excel in capturing temporal dependencies in sequential data.

4.4 Ensemble Approach:

The following techniques are used by the ensemble learning framework to combine the base classifiers' outputs: By averaging the predictions from several classifiers trained on various subsets of the data, bagging (also known as bootstrap aggregating) improves stability and accuracy.

Boosting: To iteratively improve the model by concentrating on instances that were incorrectly classified.

AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting are utilized. By using a meta-classifier—usually a logistic regression model—that learns to optimally combine the outputs of the base classifiers, stacking involves combining base classifiers.

5 EVALUATION AND VALIDATION

Benchmark EEG sleep datasets, such as the Sleep-EDF database, which includes polysomnographic recordings annotated with sleep stages, are used to validate the proposed model.

5.1 Measures of Performance

Metrics like recall, accuracy, precision, F1-score, and Cohen's kappa are used to assess performance. Through testing on unseen data and cross-validation, the robustness of the model is evaluated.

5.2 Evaluation by Comparison

The model's superiority in terms of accuracy, adaptability, and interpretability is demonstrated by comparing its performance with both state-of-the-art methods and traditional single-classifier systems. Here we provided by comparative analysis of random forest, adaboost and LSTM Models.

Fig 2: Random forest classifier for EGG

Figure 4: LSTM Classifier for EGG

Figure 3: AdaBoost Classifier for EGG

6. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

Through multi-level feature representation and ensemble learning, the proposed model offers improved accuracy, robustness, and adaptability in EEG-based sleep stage scoring. This is a significant advancement in the field. Better sleep health outcomes are achieved as a result of its interpretability and adaptive mechanisms, which make it a useful solution for both clinical and home settings. To ensure that the model is generalizable and applicable in real-world scenarios, future research will concentrate on improving adaptive mechanisms even further, investigating more advanced ensemble techniques, and validating the model on larger and more diverse datasets.

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